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NANOFACTS
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“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER THERANOSTICS”

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1. Introduction

The main goal of the NANOFACTS project is to improve the research excellence at the BioSense Institute in the field of nanomaterial development for use in cancer therapy, imaging and diagnosis, as well as strengthening the capacity of biosensor technologies at the BioSense Institute by developing research in the field of biosensors for cancer detection. One of the main aspects of improving overall research excellence is strengthening the research management and administration (RMA) skills, starting from the initial stages of project preparation when project writing skills are necessary, as well as networking and collaboration when forming a new consortium, and further on to the stage of actual project implementation i.e. management of the funded project that includes processes such as public procurement that may sometimes be challenging to young researchers without prior experience in such activities.

In order to enable BioSense researchers to achieve practical experience in the abovementioned RMA activities, NANOFACTS provides the trainings for all the phases of research project preparation and implementation, including the phase of potential technology transfer that requires the researchers to switch their roles from purely research-oriented towards entrepreneurial and commercial aspects. In this deliverable we focus on the trainings organized from the start of the second year of the project (January 1st, 2022) until December 31st, 2022.

Trainings organized in the second year of the NANOFACTS projects were dedicated to general challenges in project proposal writing, project management, project implementation and dissemination, teamwork, problem-solving, intellectual property (IP), and start-up management. Trainings were conceived to be conducive and valuable for researchers from the BioSense Institute.

2. Trainings

One of the main goals of NANOFACTS's activities within Work Package 5 implies the organisation of specific internal trainings for all BioSense (BIOS) researchers. This project's year was focused on different trainings/events where BIOS researchers had the opportunity to learn about Project proposal writing, project management, implementation, dissemination and IP. They also had an ability to learn more about main challenges in teamwork, to enhance problem-solving skills, and start-up management.

2.1 How to do a good pitch of my idea/product?

Full title of the training: “How to do a good pitch of my idea/product?”

On the 13th and 14th of April, 2022 a training dedicated to pitching and presentation skills was organized by BioSense Institute. Dr. Jelena Spajić, an assistant professor at the Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Faculty of Technical Sciences at the University of Novi Sad held the training in the multifunctional hall of the Rectory building, Novi Sad, Serbia.

The aim of the training was to give the opportunity to participants to broaden their work-wise pitching and presentation skills. On the first day of training, Jelena shared with participants her experience and knowledge regarding the topic of the training. The following day, participants had a

chance to use gained knowledge during the previous day and practice their pitching and presentation skills. They were free to choose what they'd present – a scientific paper, project, or an idea in one minute, after that, Jelena's feedback followed. Other participants were also welcomed to give their feedback and to share what they've noticed what has been done well and what could be improved, based on what they've learned. This feedback helped participants get an insight into how their colleagues see them and how they present themselves.

2.1.1 Objectives

- To learn about good practice of pitching and presenting from experts
- To broaden work-wise pitching and presentation skills
- Direct interaction of participants with the presenter
- Q&A session

2.1.2 Venues

The training was held in person on the 13th and 14th of April, 2022 in the multifunctional hall of the Rectory building, Novi Sad, Serbia.

2.1.3 Materials

Training invitation was provided via email by Sofija Merc, from BioSense's Center for Innovation and Business Development.

Presentation for the training was prepared by Dr. Jelena Spajić (**Figure 1**), an assistant professor at the Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Faculty of Technical Sciences at the University of Novi Sad.

The webinar was attended by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from BioSense, Nejra Omerović and 20 researchers from the Biosense institute in total (**Figure 2**).

Figure 1. Photos from the first day of the training “How to do a good pitch of my idea/product?” (first day)

Figure 2. Photos from the second day of the training “How to do a good pitch of my idea/product?” Nejra Omerović on the practical part of the training (second day)

2.2 How to disseminate successfully EU-funded project results

Full title of the webinar: How to disseminate successfully EU-funded project results – Expert Insights

Successful dissemination of the project results is one of the key performances in fortunate project management. Transparency of the project results is a way to promote reproducibility, progress, and trust in research, and it represents a good way for further collaboration with other partners from academia, research, and industry.

In this webinar held on the 26th of April 2022, Ms. Gabriella Lovász, Managing Director of Europa Media, and Ms. Francesca Monaco, Communication Strategist from Europa Media, shared their experience in managing dissemination and communication tasks.

2.2.1 Objectives

- Introduction about Europa Media
- Introduction about the planning processes
 - How to make dissemination and communication plan?
 - What is the best channel/tool to reach the intended audience?
- How to reach and engage audience?
- How to communicate your project properly and build a consistent visual strategy?
- What are the different types of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- Reporting: Dissemination and Communication activities
- Q&A session

2.2.2 Venues

The webinar about “How to disseminate successfully EU-funded project results” organized by EMDESK was held on April 26th 2022 at 11am, online.

Link:

- https://www.emdesk.com/academy/disseminate-successfully-eu-funded-project-results?utm_source=followup&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=webinar&utm_content=DisseminateSuccessfullyEUfundedProjectR%20esults&no-registerwall=1

2.2.3 Materials

NANOFACTS’s coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, sent an invitation for the webinar to the project team from BioSense via email. Presentation (**Figure 3**) was prepared by two experts from Europa Media, Gabriella Lovász (Managing Director) and Francesca Monaco (Communication Strategist). After the training, the presentation from the webinar was forwarded to all participants. The webinar was attended by four (4) NANOFACTS’s researchers: Dr. Slavica Savić, Minja Mladenović, Teodora Knežić and Mila Djisalov.

2.3 IP Policy, Strategy, and Processes

Figure 3. Screenshots of the “How to disseminate successfully EU-funded project results” webinar

Full title of the training: IP Policy, Strategy, and Processes: What Every Researcher and Research Manager Should Know

On the 16th of May 2022, an online training organized by SAIGE-Serbia accelerating innovation and entrepreneurship project was held. The training was about the main challenges concerning IP Policy,

Strategy, and Processes with a focuses to improve (i) the relevance and excellence of scientific research; and (ii) innovative entrepreneurship and access to finance for enterprise growth, as a way of contributing to Serbia's growth and competitiveness.

2.3.1 Objectives

- To get familiar with some main IP policies
- To improve the relevance and excellence of scientific research
- To learn how to access finance for enterprise growth
- Competitiveness in Serbia – innovative entrepreneurship

2.3.2 Venues

The training was held online on the 16th of May 2022 through Webex online platform.

The used link:

<https://saigeproject.webex.com/saigeproject/j.php?MTID=m8be787125e5efd9ccaf74973a39f16d1>

2.3.3 Materials

Presentation for the training (**Figure 4.**) was given by Mark Crowell, Senior Innovation Consultant, World Bank.

The training was attended by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from BioSense, Dr. Slavica Savić .

Figure 4. Screenshots from the training about IP Policy, Strategy, and Processes

2.4 Teamwork, creative thinking and problem solving

Full title of the trainings:

1. "Basic skills Training: Teamwork and creative thinking"
2. "Basic skills Training: Problem solving skills"

On the 29th of June 2022, the third day of NANOFACTS's training school, training about some Basic skills needed for working in a team was organized. It given by Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović, an

Associate professor of Industrial/Organizational Psychology at the University of Novi Sad, Department of Psychology, Novi Sad, Serbia (**Figure 5**).

The first training was related to Teamwork and creative thinking, wherein the first part, professor Majstorović gave an overview of some key features and issues of the team. After that, he pointed out some take-home notes about teamwork and moved to the second part of the lecture about creative thinking. Within this part, Dr. Majstorovic presented the concept and the structure of creative thinking with a lot of interaction with the audience.

The second training was about Problem-solving skills. Within this part, professor Majstorović explained how to improve problem-solving skills by explaining the Macrocognition-in-teams model (MITM). Furthermore, after the presentation, the professor invited eight students from the audience to participate in the practical challenge about creative thinking, teamwork and problem solving.

Figure 5. Presentation of Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović

2.4.1 Objectives

- To enhance knowledge about some key challenges in teamwork
- To learn more about creative thinking and its importance in science and research
- To enhance knowledge in problem solving
- Direct interaction of participants with the speaker & practical exercise
- Q&A session

2.4.2 Venues

The training about Teamwork and creative thinking was organized in the Science and Technology Park, Novi Sad, on the third day of NANOFACTS's training school (<https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>) held on 29th of June 2022 at 09:30 am.

2.4.3 Materials

Information about the lectures within the NANOFACTS's training school was primarily secured via email by Nikola Knežević, the project coordinator. Posters and leaflets containing the information about the lectures were also distributed throughout the campus of the University of Novi Sad. Minja Mladenović, dissemination manager of the NANOFACTS project further promoted it through the project's website and social media. The trainings about Teamwork and creative thinking and Problem solving were followed by fourteen (14) NANOFACTS's researchers and twenty (20) researchers from the Biosense institute in total.

Figure 6. Photos from the trainings provided by Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović

2.5 EU Horizon programme for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine

Full title of the training: EU Horizon programme for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine

On the third day of NANOFACTS's training school held on the 29th of June 2022, Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanović gave training in the EU Horizon program for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine. Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanović is a full professor from the Faculty of Technical Sciences (FTS), University of Novi Sad (UNS), Serbia with more than 15 years' experience in coordination of EU-funded projects (H2020, FP7, EUREKA, ERASMUS, CEI).

The main goal of the training that Prof. Stojanović held was related to the various H2020 calls and the main challenges faced by scientists during the preparation of project proposals (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Presentation of Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanović

2.5.1 Objectives

- To learn about H2020 in general
- To learn how to face with challenges in EU project proposal preparation
- Where to start? How to get an idea for a EU-funded projects
- Q&A

2.5.2 Venues

The training “EU Horizon programme for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine” was organized in the Science and Technology Park, Novi Sad, on the third day of NANOFACTS's training school (<https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>) held on 29th of June 2022 at 13:50 pm.

2.5.3 Materials

Information about Prof. Stojanović's lecture was primarily secured via email by Nikola Knežević, the project coordinator. Posters and leaflets containing the information about the lectures were also distributed throughout the campus of the University of Novi Sad. Minja Mladenović, dissemination manager of the NANOFACTS project further promoted it through the project's website and social media.

The training was followed by fourteen (14) NANOFACTS researchers and twenty (20) researchers from the Biosense institute in total.

Figure 8. Photos from the trainings provided by Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanović

2.6 Guidelines for project implementation

Full title of the training: Guidelines for project implementation

"Guidelines for project implementation" was another training held on the third day of NANOFACTS's training school held on the 29th of June 2022. The training was provided by Jovana Vlaškalin, Manager of the Business Development Department at BioSense Institute.

This training had the main aim to introduce the audience with the main terms and processes in project implementation phase. The purpose of the training was to make entire process closer and understandable to our colleagues in order to encourage them to apply to different calls and submit proposals. The focus was on presenting the Horizon Europe framework, with the special links to the rules and regulations of the Institute. However, the main principles presented apply to other types of projects, financed by different donors. The glimpse to a project terminology was given in the form of a vocabulary. The roadmap from the inception to phase out was presented with the special focus on the procedures and contact points withing the Institute (e.g. who is LEAR of the Institute and how to arrange all the administrative requirements when the project starts). At the end of the presentation, the links to useful materials were given.

2.6.1 Objectives

- To introduce the audience with the main terms and processes in project implementation phase
- To encourage researchers to apply to different calls and submit proposals
- The roadmap from the inception to phase out
- To provide useful materials
- Q&A session

2.6.2 Venues

The training about Guidelines for project implementation was organized in the Science and Technology Park, Novi Sad, on the third day of NANOFACTS's training school (<https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>) held on 29th of June 2022 at 14:10 pm.

2.6.3 Materials

Information about lecture held by Jovana Vlaškalin was primarily secured via email by Nikola Knežević, the project coordinator. Posters and leaflets containing the information about the lectures were also distributed throughout the campus of the University of Novi Sad. Minja Mladenović, dissemination manager of the NANOFACTS project further promoted it through the project's website and social media. The training was followed by fourteen (14) NANOFACTS researchers and twenty (20) researchers from the Biosense institute in total.

Figure 9. Photo from the trainings about Guidelines for project implementation

2.7 Creating & Managing Start-ups

Full title of the training: Creating and managing start-ups

Within the third day of NANOFACTS's training school, training about Creating and managing start-ups was held. It was given by Stavros Tsitouras, Senior Project Manager at Innovation and Business Development Department at BioSense Institute.

The overall goal of the presentation, was to provide the audience a general but comprehensive overview on how to create, launch and manage start-ups. The presentation was divided into 8 different sections, while there was a special focus on Healthcare Start-ups.

The first part of the presentation introduced participants in the start-up journey, examining the main reasons for launching a start-up. Some definitions of start-ups were presented, while the differences between start-ups and other companies were discussed. Moreover, a brief analysis of the Healthcare Start-up scene took place. In the second part, the main reasons behind start-up failures were analysed and discussed, also putting emphasis on healthcare start-ups, while tips and tricks on how to avoid failing were shared. The Discovery phase was the next section. Ways to get good start-up ideas and how to evaluate them were the main points of discussion. The validation phase followed where ideas on numerous validation approaches were presented together with a detailed analysis for the creation and usefulness of an MVP (Minimum Viable Product). The next part included the efficiency phase. Financing options for start-ups were discussed together with scaling up techniques and business models, while the building of a start-up team together with time management aspects, were tackled. The next part of the presentation concentrated on the growth

phase, where fundraising options were presented together with numerous growth strategies. Finally, start-up exit strategies were presented and analysed, while the session ended with some final remarks and conclusions stemming from the overall presentation.

2.7.1 Objectives

- To introduce participants in the start-up journey
- To examine the main reasons for launching a start-up
- Brief analysis of the Healthcare Start-up scene
- Ways to get good start-up ideas
- Financing options for start-ups
- Start-up exit strategies analysis
- Q&A session

2.7.2 Venues

The training about Creating and managing start-ups was organized in the Science and Technology Park, Novi Sad, on the third day of NANOFACTS's training school (<https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>) held on 29th of June 2022 at 15:05 pm.

2.7.3 Materials

Information about lecture held by Stavros Tsitouras was primarily secured via email by Nikola Knežević, the project coordinator. Posters and leaflets containing the information about the lectures were also distributed throughout the campus of the University of Novi Sad. Minja Mladenović, dissemination manager of the NANOFACTS project further promoted it through the project's website and social media. The training was followed by fourteen (14) NANOFACTS's researchers and twenty (20) researchers from the Biosense institute in total.

Figure 10. Photos from the trainings about Creating and managing startups

3. Conclusion

One of the goals of the NANOFACTS project is to develop research management and administration (RMA) skills of participating researchers, in order to enable them to competitively participate in current and new research activities, secure new funding, generate results of the highest quality and publish them in high-impact peer-reviewed journals.

Therefore, the organized trainings and presentations concerning RMA skills in the second year of the project implementation concerned wide range of soft skills to be exploited in the future. The trainings were carefully chosen to balance between various skills needed for future generation of scientist capable of leading research and research groups but also transforming their results onto market potential product.

4. Annex

4.1 The list of attendees on the third day of NANOFACTS training school

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Radojica Šolak	Teaching Associate PhD student	University of Novi Sad
2.	VEBOSJA MAŠTAROVIĆ	PROFESSOR	UNIV. OF NOVISAD
3.	MINJA MLADENOVIĆ	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
4.	PETAR DAVIDOVIĆ	RESEARCH ASSISTANT	FACULTY OF SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD
5.	Sura Joksović	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	Biosense Institute
6.	Mila Đisalo	Junior Research assistant	Biosense Institute
7.	Mirjana Mundić	Junior Researcher	Biosense Institute
8.	MARKO RADOVIĆ	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
9.	Čučurević Čest	Junior researcher	Biosense
10.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	Biosense
11.	Nerena Jaćimović	Student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade
12.	Milica Pena	student	Faculty of Sciences
13.	Jelena Radević	student	Faculty of Sciences
14.	Teodora Despotovski	student	Faculty of sciences
15.	GORANA Ilić	STUDENT	Faculty of sciences
16.	Peđa ERTIĆ	Prof	TU Wien
17.	Biljana Javic	FOOD ENGINEERING PHD STUDENT	FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD
18.	Daniela Petrović	PROFESSOR	UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD
19.	Njira Omerović	Junior Researcher	Biosense Institute
20.	GIJANA SPASOJEVIĆ	RESEARCHER	FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD
21.	Jelena Kijac	Student	Faculty of Science

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

22.	Ksenija Đurđević	Student	Faculty of Sciences
23.	Ida Zahović	Researcher	TF NS
24.	Dušan Radonić	student	PMF
25.	Dušan Žuković	Student	PMF
26.	Miroslav Dočas	Student	FTN
27.	Vesna Teofilović	researcher	TF NS
28.	ОТЕРАН ЈАРУЊ	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
29.	Ivana Podunavac	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
30.	Aleksandra Jovanović	Junior. Research Assistant	BIOSENSE
31.	Francesco Plozis	RESEARCHER	PLASTORE
32.	PARLA GABRIELLA PACCIONI	Researcher	PLASTORE
33.	NATAŠA HAREVSKI	JUNIOR ASSISTANT	BIO3
34.	MAJA KUMIČA	PROJECT MANAGER	BIO3
35.	Evan Bobinčić	RESEARCHER	BIO3
36.	GORDA STAJKONIĆ	FULL PROFESSOR, VUS	UNG <i>Sp CF</i>
37.	Sandra Jajčić	student	FTN
38.	Nina Ectović	student	FTN
39.	Jelena Derić	student	FTN
40.	NIKOLA KOLEVIĆ	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIO3
41.	Jasna Vlaselin	Manager	BIO3
42.	DINH MAI	Researcher	TCD
43.	Oli Gobbo	Researcher	TCD

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 29. 6. 2022.

44.	Jelena Jović	Senior Researcher	BioSense
45.	Ljiljana Janjusević	Senior Researcher	BioSense
46.	Evon Bobrinča	researcher	BIOS
47.	BOJIS POPOVIĆ	Full professor	Faculty of Agriculture
48.	Stavros Tsitouras	Senior Project Manager	BioSenia
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